

PREPERATION, CHARACTERIZATION AND PROPERTIES OF NOVOLAC TYPE PHENOLIC/SiO₂ HYBRID ORGANIC/INORGANIC NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIALS BY SOL-GEL METHOD

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SUMMARY : This article describes the preparation of novolac-type phenolic resin/silica hybrid organic-inorganic nanocomposite, using a sol-gel process. The coupling agent was used to improve the interface between the organic and inorganic phases. The effect of the structure of the nanocomposite on its physical and chemical properties is discussed.

The coupling agent reacts with the resin to form covalent bonds. The structure of the modified hybrid nanocomposites was identified using a Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscope. The silica network was characterized by nuclear magnetic resonance imaging technique (²⁹Si NMR). Results reveal that Q₄ (tetra-substituted) and T₃ (tri-substituted) are the dominant microstructures. The size of the silica in the phenolic resin was characterized using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The size of the particles of inorganic silica in the modified-system was less than 100 nm. The nanocomposite exhibited good transparency. Moreover, thermal and mechanical properties exhibited significant improvement. The modified hybrid composite exhibited favorable thermal properties. The temperature at which the weight loss of 5% of sample(Td₅) occurred increased from 281°C to 350°C. The flexural strength increased by 6~30%. The limiting oxygen index (L.O.I.) of the nanocomposite reached 37 and the materials were qualified by the Underwriters Laboratory (U.L.) 94V-0 test. These materials possess excellent flame-retardant properties.

KEYWORDS: phenolic resin, sol-gel, hybrid, nanocomposite, silica, and thermal properties

INTRODUCTION

Combinations of organic polymer matrices and inorganic particles have been developed over past decades as the organic-inorganic hybrid materials. These materials possess unique properties with improved physical, mechanical and thermal properties. The material properties of physically mixed components depend on the content of the particles, their adhesion to the polymer matrix, the uniformity of particle dispersion, and other factors. In the past decade, various elastomers, thermoplastics and thermosetting matrices, have been reinforced with inorganic fillers^[1-7]. These organic-inorganic systems formed in-situ by the sol-gel technique have become a new class of composites, organic-inorganic hybrid materials. The new hybrid materials exhibit a controllable combination of the characteristics of both organic polymers and inorganic glasses. The size of the formed inorganic particles, hence, normally of nanometer size, hence, these hybrid materials are also called nanocomposites.^[1-7]

The sol-gel process is well known as a useful technique for preparing organic-inorganic hybrid materials. In hybrid materials, the inorganic phase is formed within an organic polymer matrix by a sol-gel process. In the simple sol-gel process, hydrolysis and condensation reactions of inorganic alkoxides occur in a cosolvent that contains water, catalyzed by acid or base at low temperature^[8-10]. The sol-gel process provides a method for preparing a variety of organic-inorganic hybrid materials at the molecular level^[11-18]. The in-situ development of a three-dimensional cross-linked inorganic network structure uses an organic precursor, such as an alkoxy derivative of a metal like Si or Ti. The most common precursor is tetraethoxysilane (TEOS), which yields a silica network.

The microstructure of the metal oxide obtained using a sol-gel process depends on the hydrolysis and condensation reactions, which are generally controlled by the pH of the solution^[19-21]. In the acid-catalyzed reaction, the hydrolysis step is faster than the condensation step, resulting in a more extended and less highly branched network structure. In the base-catalyzed reaction, condensation is faster than hydrolysis, resulting in a highly condensed species, which may agglomerate into fine particles. Furthermore, the sol-gel process involves a very complex reaction, involving many variables such as the type of alkoxide, pH, the amount of water, the kinds of cosolvent, the temperature and the drying method, among others^[22-25].

Phenolic resin is a thermoset resin that is used in a broad range of applications, such as paints, adhesives and composites. Many attempts have been made to enhance the toughness and thermal properties of phenolic resin^[26-29]. With reference to preparing hybrid materials, the sol-gel method can be utilized to incorporate inorganic components into the phenolic resin and thus improve its properties. Haraguchi et al.^[26,27] and Ma, et al.^[28,29] have investigated such systems.

This study employs the sol-gel technique to prepare the novolac phenolic resin/SiO₂

organic/inorganic hybrid materials. Examining morphology and outward appearance has elucidated various degrees of phase separation. The coupling agent, 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTS), was used to increase the compatibility between the organic (novolac phenolic resin) and inorganic phases (silica network) and thereby reduce the phase separation. Mechanical and thermal properties were also considered.

EXPERIMENTS

Materials

The phenolic resin used was of the novolac type (PF1120HH), and was obtained from the Chang-Chun Plastics Co., Taiwan. Tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) and the coupling agent, 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTS), was purchased from Acros Organics Co., New Jersey, U.S.A.. Hexamethylene tetra mine (Hexa) was used as a curing agent, and was obtained from Acros Organics Co., New Jersey, U.S.A..

Preparation of modified-phenolic resin/SiO₂ hybrid materials

The hybrid materials were prepared by mixing two solutions, A and B. Solution A was prepared as follows. 5 g of neat novolac type phenolic resin was dissolved in THF; the solid content was kept at 50%. 2g of 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPTS) was used as a coupling agent to modify the phenolic resin. GPTS was added slowly into the solution of the phenolic resin and THF, the GPTS content was 10 phr (parts per hundred parts of resin, as a weight ratio). Then, the mixture was stirred at 70°C for 20~24 hours. The modified phenolic resin was obtained by a ring-opening reaction of GPTS with hydroxyl groups, in phenolic resin. This modified-phenolic resin/THF solution was called solution A.

Solution B consisted of TEOS/H₂O/THF/HCl. In solution B, 1.25 g of TEOS was added to 1.25 g of THF solvent. The TEOS content was 20 wt% (as a proportion of the weight of phenolic resin). The TEOS/H₂O molar ratio was 1:4, hence, 0.024 grams of H₂O was added to the mixture. HCl was used as a catalyst for hydrolysis, i.e. it was 0.03wt% in the solution. Then, the mixture was stirred at 25°C for 30 min.

Hexamethylene tetramine (Hexa) was used as a curing agent, 0.6 g Hexa was added into solution A. Then, solutions A and B were mixed. The final solution was cast into aluminum dishes and aged at room temperature for two to three days. Then the samples were dried at a rate of 2 °C/hr from 25 °C to 80 °C and then kept at 80 °C for 2 hr. The samples were finally cured at 120 °C for 4 hours, 180 °C for 2hr, and post-cured at 230 °C for 8hr.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization

Figure 1 shows the FT-IR spectra of the reaction between novolac type phenolic resin and 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane. The figure displays the change of the characteristic peak of the epoxy group of 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane at 914cm^{-1} . The ring-opening reaction of 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane caused the peak at 914 cm^{-1} to disappear and moved the bending red-shift of C-H out of plane to 889 cm^{-1} . The characteristic peak of the hydroxyl group at $3000\sim 3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ became broader since the ring-opening reaction generated different hydroxyl group types. The result confirms that the novolac-type phenolic resin reacted with 3-glycidoxypropyl-trimethoxysilane at various times.

Figure 2 illustrates the solid-state ^{29}Si NMR spectra of the modified hybrid nanocomposite. Condensed siloxane species for TEOS, the silica network structure of the hybrid nanocomposite in which a silicon atom through mono-, di, tri, tetra-substituted siloxane bonds, are designated as Q^1 , Q^2 , Q^3 , Q^4 , respectively. The chemical shifts at -91 , -101 and -110 ppm correspond to Q^2 , Q^3 and Q^4 , respectively, agree closely with the values in the literature ^[32,33]. 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane with mono-, di-, tri-, tetra-substituted siloxane bonds is designated as T^1 , T^2 , T^3 . The chemical shifts at -51 , -58 and -65 ppm correspond to T^1 , T^2 and T^3 , respectively, confirm the values in the literature ^[32,33]. Results reveal that Q^4 and T^3 are the major microstructures in the modified hybrid nanocomposite; restated, formed a network structure. The unmodified hybrid shows a similar trend.

Morphological Properties

The compatibility between the organic (polymer) and the inorganic phases (silica) strongly affects the thermal, mechanical and optical properties. The morphology of the fractured surfaces was elucidated by SEM and a mapping technique to determine the size distribution of silica and micro-phase separation in the hybrid matrix. Figure 3 presents SEM microphotographs of the fractured surface of the unmodified hybrid composite and the modified hybrid nanocomposite. Figure 4 presents the mapping image of modified hybrid materials. When the coupling agent was added, the size of the silica cluster decreased and the phase separation was improved. The size of the cluster of silica could be controlled below 100 nm . This phenomenon reveals the good miscibility between organic (polymer) and inorganic (silica) phases. Figures 4 and 5 were obtained by EDX spectroscopy. Figure 4 shows the Si-mapping image of the modified hybrid nanocomposite. The Si-mapping image verifies that the silica particles were distributed uniformly in the modified hybrid nanocomposite. Consequently, when the GPTS content was 10 phr , the modified hybrid materials were nanocomposites, with good transparency, as neat phenolic resin.

Figure 1 FT-IR spectrum of GPTS-Phenolic resin at different reaction times. (a) Initial, (b) $t=6\text{hr}$, (c) $t=20\text{hr}$, (d) final.

Figure 2 ^{29}Si -NMR spectra of GPTS-Phenolic resin/ SiO_2 modified hybrid nanocomposite.

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Figure 3 The SEM microphotographs of fractured surface of unmodified hybrid composite and modified hybrid nanocomposite.

Figure 4 The Si-mapping image of modified hybrid nanocomposite.

Figure 5 The EDX spectrum of modified hybrid nanocomposites

Thermal Properties and Flame Retardance

Figure 6 presents TGA curves of the hybrid composites with various coupling agent (GPTS) content. The TGA curves range from room temperature to 800°C in an atmosphere of N₂. They show that, the char yields of the hybrid materials increased with the amount of GPTS. Increasing char formation reduces the production of combustible gases, decreases exothermicity during pyrolysis reaction and inhibits the thermal conductivity of the burning materials. When the silica network was added, the degradation decelerates. The inorganic components can suppress the degradation of the nanocomposite. The char yield was correlated with the flame retardance. The condensed phase mechanism improves the flame retardancy of the hybrid materials. Table 1 summarizes the char yield, T_{d5} and T_{d10} (the temperature of degradation of composite at which the weight loss is 5% or 10%, respectively) of the hybrid materials with various amounts of coupling agent (GPTS). T_{d5} and T_{d10} of the neat novolac type phenolic resin were 281.8°C and 365.3°C, respectively. T_{d5} and T_{d10} of the hybrid material (GPTS content = 0 phr) were 315.1°C and 401.1°C. As GPTS content increased to 10 phr, T_{d5} and T_{d10} of the hybrid material increased to 350.8°C and 439.9°C, respectively. The char yield of the hybrid materials increased from 56.13 wt% to 63.99 wt%. The inorganic components of the silica enhanced the thermal stability of the hybrid materials.

The flame retardant properties of the hybrid composites were examined by measuring the Limiting Oxygen Index (L.O.I.) and the Underwriters' Laboratory 94 (UL-94) Test of the hybrid composites. Table 2 reveals a significant increase in L.O.I. (from 33 to 37). This finding indicates that incorporating silica significantly promotes the flame retardance of novolac-type phenolic resin. The result is consistent with the char yield data. Furthermore, the U.L. test was applied to probe the flame retardance of the hybrid composites and to rank them. Table 2 shows the results of the U.L. test. Results show that neat phenolic resin may be

classified as 94V-1 grade. The nanocomposite (GPTS content 10 phr) can also be classified as 94V-0 grade.

The hybrid phenolic nanocomposite with good flame retardancy and excellent thermal stability is considered to be sufficient for its application as a flame retardant material.

Figure 6 TGA curves of neat phenolic resin (a), unmodified hybrid composite (b) and modified hybrid nanocomposite(c).

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Table 1 Comparison of the degradation temperature at 5%, 10% weight loss and the char yield of neat phenolic resin, unmodified hybrid composite and modified hybrid nanocomposite at N₂ atmosphere

SYSTEMS	Temperature of 5% Weight Loss (°C)	Temperature of 10% Weight Loss (°C)	Char Yeild (wt%)
Neat phenolic resin	281.8	365.3	56.13
Unmodified hybrid composite	315.1	401.1	61.37
Modified hybrid nanocomposite	350.8	439.9	63.28

Table 2 The UL-94 and L.O.I. test results of neat phenolic resin, unmodified hybrid composite and modified hybrid nanocomposite.

SYSTEMS	Flaming drops	Cotton ignited	UL-94 standard	L.O.I
Neat phenolic resin	N/A ^(a)	N/A	94V-1	33
Unmodified hybrid composite	N/A	N/A	94V-0	36
Modified hybrid nanocomposite	N/A	N/A	94V-0	37

a : Not Available

CONCLUSIONS

New phenolic/silica hybrid nanocomposites, synthesized by the sol-gel process, have been prepared. The silica network of hybrid composites was investigated using ²⁹Si NMR. The dominant microstructure of the modified hybrid nanocomposite was that of Q₄ and T₃. SEM microphotographs revealed that the silica particles were aggregated in the unmodified hybrid composite. However, the size of the cluster of silica particles could be controlled within 100 nm in the modified hybrid nanocomposite. The Si-mapping image confirms that the silica particles were distributed uniformly in the modified hybrid nanocomposite. The nanocomposite exhibits good transparency, close to that of neat phenolic resin. Silica-containing hybrid composites have a higher thermal stability and char yield. Flammability test data showed these nanocomposites possess L.O.I. 37 and U.L. 94V-0 characters, therefore, the modified hybrid nanocomposites exhibited excellent fire-resistant properties.

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